

Empirical Research

Financial Innovation and Industrial Diversification in Macao: The Pandemic's Moderating Role and Managerial Implications

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Abstract

Macao's economy encountered challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, exacerbated by its heavy reliance on the gaming sector. Industrial diversification is critical for sustainable development. The financial industry demonstrated robust vitality, with value-added growth persisting despite the pandemic, supporting efforts to sustain diversification and enhance risk prevention. Financial innovation, including traditional financial innovation and financial technology innovation, is promising. This study employs seven indicators to evaluate financial innovation using principal component analysis and factor analysis, revealing significant improvement in Macao's financial innovation levels over the pandemic years (2020–2022). It further examines the relationship between financial innovation and industrial diversification, with the pandemic period incorporated as a moderating variable. Findings indicate that financial innovation reduced industrial diversification in non-pandemic years but enhanced diversification during the pandemic, driven by a significant interaction between financial innovation and the pandemic. The study acknowledges limitations and offers policy and managerial recommendations to guide future development.

Note: Both Macao and Macau are recognized as valid official names. Because the majority of government documents use Macao, this study uses Macao throughout, except for University of Macau, its address, and specific documents that use Macau.

Keywords: financial innovation, fintech, industrial diversification, Macao/Macau economy, COVID-19 impact, principal component analysis, factor analysis, economic policy, financial resilience

Subjects: #Finance, #EconomicDevelopment, #RegionalEconomics, #InnovationStudies, #PolicyAnalysis, #StatisticalMethods, #Sustainability, #CrisisManagement

1. Introduction

Macao's economy faced significant challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, amplified by its heavy reliance on the gaming sector, which exposed the risks of a mono-industrial structure. The pandemic highlighted the need for moderate industrial diversification, defined as balanced growth across multiple sectors, to ensure sustainable development. Despite the economic downturn, the financial industry showed remarkable resilience, continuing to grow and contributing significantly to economic stability. Macao's gaming sector recovery in July 2025 further underscores this strength, with gross gaming revenue surging 19% year-on-year to MOP 22.1 billion (USD 2.7 billion) and approaching 90% of pre-pandemic (2019) levels, supported by a 32% increase in premium bettor spending. This upturn aligns with tourism growth, as June 2025 recorded 2.9 million tourist arrivals, representing 93% of 2019 levels (Times Reporter, 2025). This resilience prompts exploring how diversification can be sustained while enhancing risk prevention. Financial innovation, encompassing advancements like analytics driven by artificial intelligence (hereafter referred to as AI-driven analytics) and digital payments, offers a promising path forward.

This study employs seven indicators to construct a composite evaluation system using principal component analysis and factor analysis, revealing a marked improvement in Macao's financial innovation levels during the pandemic years (2020–2022). The investigation examines the relationship between financial innovation and industrial diversification, with the pandemic as a moderating variable. Findings show that financial innovation reduced industrial diversification in non-pandemic years but enhanced diversification during the pandemic, driven by a significant interaction with the pandemic. The study acknowledges limitations and offers practical policy recommendations to guide future development, contributing to Macao's sustainable economic growth (Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service, 2022, 2023).

Recently, the Macao government has introduced policies to support economic diversification and financial-sector growth, aligning with regional initiatives like the Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macao Greater Bay Area framework. These efforts aim to reduce reliance on gaming by leveraging the financial sector's resilience. Although Macao's land area is limited, its comprehensive infrastructure supports continuous innovation. Studies on Macao's financial innovation are scarce, often overlooking its unique economic characteristics. This study fills gaps in the literature by analyzing financial innovation's role in Macao's industrial diversification under the pandemic's impact, offering case data for marketing, sustainability, and regional economics while providing policymakers with actionable insights.

2. Macao's Situations and Trends

Macao's economy, long dominated by gaming but striving for diversification, faces ongoing challenges as 2025 gaming revenue projections signal a robust recovery toward pre-pandemic levels. According to the monthly gross gaming revenue data from the Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Gaming Inspection and Coordination Bureau (2012–2022) and the GDP data from Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service (2012–2022), gross gaming revenue surged to a historic peak of MOP 360.7 billion in 2013. From 2012 through 2014, the gaming sector consistently contributed over 79% of Macao's nominal GDP, underscoring its dominant role in the local economy. However, due to regulatory tightening and shifts in mainland visitation patterns, the industry experienced a sharp contraction from 2015 to 2016, followed by a partial recovery in 2017–2018 before declining slightly in 2019 to MOP 292.3 billion, still well above 2015–2016 lows, representing approximately 67.3% of GDP. Gross gaming revenue then sank to MOP 60.4 billion, MOP 86.9 billion, and MOP 42.2 billion in 2020, 2021, and 2022, respectively, during the pandemic. This

trajectory illustrates both the centrality of gaming to Macao's economic structure and its susceptibility to external shocks, policy interventions, and global health crises.

The COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022) disrupted Macao's stable industry structure, with the gaming sector experiencing a significant contraction. In contrast, the financial and real estate sectors demonstrated resilience, contributing increasingly to economic output. This shift underscores the vulnerability of Macao's mono-industrial economy, historically dominated by gaming (Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service, 2022). The pandemic caused a sharp economic downturn, halving Macao's GDP due to suspensions in work and production and over-reliance on a single industry. Despite earlier diversification efforts, progress was limited, with many sectors failing to achieve expected growth.

Emerging industries, supported by policies like the "1 + 4" economic development strategy (consisting of integrated tourism and leisure plus "Big Health" industry emphasizing traditional Chinese medicine; modern financial services; high and new technology; convention, exhibition, sports, and commercial and trade industries), showed mixed performance, with finance leading the way. Recent efforts by casino operators including Sands China, Galaxy Entertainment, and MGM China have advanced diversification through expanded luxury hotel offerings and entertainment events like concerts in 2025 (Times Reporter, 2025), aligning with the "1 + 4" strategy to boost non-gaming revenue streams. Revenue showed monthly increases with peaks during holidays like National Day, Christmas, and Spring Festival, but growth rates fluctuated, indicating ongoing challenges for the gaming industry. Meanwhile, the financial sector continued to grow throughout the pandemic, outperforming other industries and highlighting its potential as a driver of diversification. These trends suggest that financial technology innovation, bolstered by government support and new technologies, may open new prospects for Macao's industrial diversification (National Bureau of Statistics of China, 2012–2022).

3. Literature Review

3.1. Research on Financial Innovation

The concept of innovation refers to novel or qualitative changes in products, processes, markets, input sources, and organizational structures (Arthur, 2009). These activities drive economic development. Financial innovation, by extension, involves creating new financial products and technologies, restructuring organizations, and developing market mechanisms while promoting their adoption within the financial system (Lerner & Tufano, 2011). These foundational concepts shape the classification of financial innovations (Khraisha & Arthur, 2018). Over the past two decades, traditional financial innovations have spanned systems, markets, products, institutions, resources, technologies, and management practices. Recent definitions incorporate emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things. Financial innovation stems from household borrowing and saving behaviors, financial sector profit incentives, firms' financing needs, and improved risk identification and management (Haliassos, 2013).

After the 2008 financial crisis, financial innovation sparks extensive debate. Many studies identify it as a key determinant of the modern financial system and global economy (Shiller, 2008; Qamruzzaman & Wei, 2018). However, some scholars argue that excessive financial innovation contributed to the crisis (Boz & Mendoza, 2014; Hausman & Johnston, 2014). Balancing its benefits and risks, therefore, warrants careful consideration.

3.2. Research on Industrial Diversification

Industrial diversification refers to the process through which economic activity spreads more equally across sectors before eventually re-specializing, producing a U-shaped relationship with per-capita income (Imbs & Wacziarg, 2003). In academic literature, industrial diversification often serves to examine the relationship between diversification and economic development, underscoring its importance for resilience and growth. For instance, an industry analysis in the European region finds that innovation capacity constitutes a critical component of economic diversity and resilience (Xiao et al., 2018). During economic expansion, regions with more concentrated industries exhibit lower unemployment; in downturns, those with diversified structures perform better (Brown & Greenbaum, 2017). Industrial diversification is driven by multiple factors, with technological innovation as the primary catalyst, alongside significant contributions from market demand and resource endowments.

Existing studies on Macao's industrial diversification reveal a mono-industrial economy with weak risk-resistance, a condition laid bare by the COVID-19 pandemic. Consequently, Macao urgently needs to develop additional industries to enhance economic diversification and mitigate risks. This transformation should proceed through internal diversification and deeper regional integration (e.g., the Guangdong–Macao In-Depth Cooperation Zone in Hengqin), thereby promoting balanced economic diversification and sustainable development (Liu & Lin, 2024).

In summary, past research has examined Macao's reliance on a single-industry structure and proposed solutions from multiple perspectives. Financial innovation serves as a robust driver, demonstrating strong resilience even under extreme conditions. Given that Macao's financial sector is still emerging, related research is scarce. At present, studies on the relationship between financial innovation and industrial diversification in Macao, particularly in the context of the pandemic, remain limited. The nature of this relationship and its evolution require further in-depth investigation, constituting the research question of this study.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Framework for This Study

The research framework for this study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Research Framework for Financial Innovation and Industrial Diversification Analysis

Using m financial innovation indicators in principal component analysis and p original variables in factor analysis, this study extracts p principal components and m latent factors, respectively. Principal component composite scores C (from principal component analysis)

and factor composite scores Q (from factor analysis) are then derived from these analytical methods. Additionally, the pandemic factor Z is incorporated as a moderator variable to develop a moderating effect model, examining the impact and underlying mechanisms of financial innovation on industrial diversification.

4.2. Theoretical Analysis

4.2.1. Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis (Hotelling, 1933; Pearson, 1901) involves the following four steps:

Step 1. Standardize data. Assuming there are m indicator variables for principal component analysis, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m , there are n evaluation objects in total, and the value of the j^{th} indicator of the i^{th} evaluation object is x_{ij} . Convert the values of each indicator into standardized indicators \tilde{x}_{ij} :

$$\tilde{x}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j}{s_j}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) standardizes each raw indicator into a z-score to place all variables on a common scale. Among them, $\bar{x}_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij}$ is the sample mean of the j^{th} indicator, and s_j is the sample standard deviation, as defined in Equation (2):

$$s_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) defines the sample standard deviation s_j used in Equation (1) for standardizing the j^{th} indicator.

Step 2. Establish a correlation coefficient matrix R between variables.

$$R = (r_{ij})_{m \times m} \quad (3)$$

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{x}_{ki} \times \tilde{x}_{kj}}{n-1} (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m) \quad (4)$$

Equation (3) constructs the correlation matrix R to capture pairwise linear relationships among those standardized indicators. Equation (4) defines each correlation coefficient r_{ij} between the i^{th} and j^{th} indicators. In the formula, $r_{ii} = 1$ (perfect correlation of an indicator with itself) and $r_{ij} = r_{ji}$ (symmetry of the correlation matrix), where r_{ij} is the correlation coefficient between the i^{th} and j^{th} indicators.

Step 3. Calculate the eigenvalues of the correlation coefficient matrix R , $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_m \geq 0$, and corresponding feature vectors u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m . Among them, $u_j = (u_{1j}, u_{2j}, \dots, u_{mj})^T$. Compose m new indicator vectors from feature vectors:

$$\begin{cases} y_1 = u_{11}\tilde{x}_1 + u_{21}\tilde{x}_2 + \dots + u_{m1}\tilde{x}_m \\ y_2 = u_{12}\tilde{x}_1 + u_{22}\tilde{x}_2 + \dots + u_{m2}\tilde{x}_m \\ \dots \\ y_m = u_{1m}\tilde{x}_1 + u_{2m}\tilde{x}_2 + \dots + u_{mm}\tilde{x}_m \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) forms each principal component as a weighted sum of the standardized indicators using the eigenvector weights. In the formula, y_1 is the first principal component, y_2 is the second principal component, y_m is the m^{th} principal component. Here, u_{ij} are elements of

the eigenvector $u_j = (u_{1j}, u_{2j}, \dots, u_{mj})^T$, corresponding to the eigenvalue λ_j . In this study, the first $p = 2$ principal components are retained and denoted as C_1 and C_2 in subsequent analyses (see Section 5.2.2 and Equations (19)–(21)).

Step 4. Write the principal components and calculate the composite score.

Calculate the contribution rate and the cumulative contribution rate of eigenvalues λ_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, m$):

$$b_j = \frac{\lambda_j}{\sum_{k=1}^m \lambda_k} (j = 1, 2, \dots, m) \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) computes each component's contribution rate by dividing its eigenvalue by the sum of all eigenvalues. The cumulative contribution rate of the first p principal components:

$$a_p = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^p \lambda_k}{\sum_{k=1}^m \lambda_k} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) calculates the cumulative contribution rate to decide how many components to retain. When the cumulative contribution rate a_p of the principal components y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p approaches 1 ($a_p = 0.85, 0.90, 0.95$), the first p principal components (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p) are selected to replace the original m indicator variables, thus enabling composite analysis of the p principal components. Calculate the composite score:

$$C = \sum_{j=1}^p b_j y_j \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) combines the selected principal components into one composite score, weighting each by its contribution rate, where b_j is the contribution rate of the j^{th} principal component.

4.2.2. Factor Analysis

Factor analysis, pioneered by Spearman (1904), models relationships among variables to identify underlying factors. For p original variables x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p$), which may be related or independent, standardizing x_i yields a new variable z_i , enabling the establishment of a factor analysis model as follows:

$$z_i = a_{i1}F_1 + a_{i2}F_2 + \dots + a_{im}F_m + c_i U_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, p) \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) models each standardized financial innovation indicator ($z_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$) as a sum of m common factors F_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) plus a unique factor U_i . The common factors F_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) appear in the expression of each indicator, and their meanings are interpreted based on the specific context of financial innovation. The unique factors U_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p$) are specific to each indicator z_i . Coefficients a_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p; j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) are the factor loadings, and c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p$) is the coefficient of the unique factor U_i . $A = a_{ij}$ is the factor loading matrix.

Modern factor analysis, as developed by Thurstone (1947), extends this framework with eigenvalue decomposition and factor rotation. Calculate the eigenvalues of the correlation coefficient matrix R , $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_m \geq 0$, and corresponding feature vectors u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m , among them, $u_j = (u_{1j}, u_{2j}, \dots, u_{pj})^T$. The initial factor loading matrix is:

$$A = [\sqrt{\lambda_1}u_1 \quad \sqrt{\lambda_2}u_2 \quad \dots \quad \sqrt{\lambda_m}u_m] \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) derives the initial factor loading matrix from the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the correlation matrix.

Factor rotation is defined as follows. Based on the initial factor loading matrix, select m common factors based on interpretability or eigenvalue criteria. Rotate the factor loading matrix to obtain the matrix $B = AT$, where T is an orthogonal matrix. Construct factor model:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{x}_1 = b_{11}F_1 + \dots + b_{1m}F_m \\ \dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots \\ \tilde{x}_p = b_{p1}F_1 + \dots + b_{pm}F_m \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) expresses each standardized financial innovation indicator ($\tilde{x}_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$) as a linear combination of m common factors based on the rotated factor model, where coefficients b_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p; j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) are derived from the rotated factor loading matrix. Orthogonal rotation (e.g., varimax) maximizes the variance of the squared loadings, enhancing interpretability of the common factors F_1 and F_2 .

Calculate factor scores using regression methods:

$$F_j = b_{j1}\tilde{x}_1 + \dots + b_{jp}\tilde{x}_p, j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (12)$$

$$[b_1^T \quad b_2^T \quad \dots \quad b_m^T] = R^{-1}A \quad (13)$$

Equation (12) computes factor scores (e.g., F_1, F_2) as a linear combination of p standardized variables using coefficients from the rotated factor loading matrix. Equation (13) defines the factor score coefficients, relating all observed variables to m common factors in one matrix equation.

To clarify notation, in principal component analysis, m denotes the number of original indicators ($X_1-X_7, m = 7$), and p denotes the number of retained principal components ($C_1, C_2, p = 2$). In factor analysis, p denotes the number of original variables ($X_1-X_7, p = 7$), and m denotes the number of latent factors ($F_1, F_2, m = 2$). This notation reflects the focus of principal component analysis on reducing m indicators to p components to maximize variance and the aim of factor analysis to model p variables with m latent factors to explain covariance, consistent with standard practices (Hotelling, 1933; Thurstone, 1947).

4.2.3. Moderating Effect

The moderating effect refers to whether the influence of the independent variable X on the dependent variable Y is affected by the moderator variable Z . If the relationship between variable X and variable Y is a function of Z , Z is called the moderator variable (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

When conducting moderating effect analysis, it is necessary to center the independent and moderator variables by subtracting their means (James & Brett, 1984):

$$\tilde{X}_i = X_i - \bar{X}_i \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) centers the independent or moderator variable X_i by subtracting its mean \bar{X}_i , preparing it for interaction-term creation, where i indexes observations.

The moderator variables can be qualitative or quantitative, and there are different analysis methods for moderating effect models for different types of data (Fang et al., 2015):

$$\text{Model 1: } Y = \beta_0 + \alpha X + \varepsilon \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Model 2: } Y = \beta_0 + \alpha X + bZ + \varepsilon \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Model 3: } Y = \beta_0 + \alpha X + bZ + cXZ + \varepsilon \quad (17)$$

Equation (15) is the baseline regression model (Model 1) in the Baron and Kenny (1986) moderation framework. It tests the direct effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) without the moderator. Here, X represents financial innovation indicators (traditional financial innovation or financial technology innovation, as derived from principal component analysis or factor analysis), and Y is the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity, measuring industrial diversification. Equation (16) extends that regression by adding the moderator variable's direct effect. Equation (17) completes the moderation test by including the interaction term between the independent variable and the moderator.

To verify the effectiveness of moderating effects, it is common to analyze the estimation and testing of the interaction term coefficient c . If c is significant, that is, rejecting the null hypothesis of $c = 0$, it indicates that the moderating effect of Z is significant. Additionally, it is possible to observe the changes in R^2 from Model 2 to Model 3 to determine if the ΔF value is significant. If significant, it indicates a significant change in R^2 .

5. Empirical Analysis

5.1. Datasets

5.1.1. Data Selection

This study evaluates Macao's financial innovation, denoted Q , defined as the development of novel financial instruments, services, or processes that enhance efficiency and access in financial systems (Frame & White, 2014). It comprises traditional financial innovation, denoted F_1 , which includes advancements in banking operations, such as financial industry employment, financial institutions' value-added ratio, loan-to-deposit ratio, financial industry financing, and financial system asset ratio, denoted X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 , and X_5 , respectively (Tufano, 2003), and financial technology innovation, denoted F_2 , which includes technology-driven advancements, such as new financial technology companies and government investment in financial technology, denoted X_6 and X_7 , respectively (Philippon, 2017). These indicators, detailed in Table 1 and shown in Figure 2, are analyzed using factor analysis in Section 5.3.2 and aligned with financial data from the Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service (2012–2022) and National Bureau of Statistics of China (2012–2022).

Industrial diversification, conceptualized as the process of spreading economic activity across multiple sectors to enhance economic resilience, is commonly measured in academia and government using the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity (Research and Economic Analysis Division, 2011; see also Hackbart & Anderson, 1975, for a foundational discussion). In this study, industrial diversification is operationalized as the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity as shown in Equation (18), which serves as the dependent variable (Y) in regression analyses, quantifying the evenness of output distribution across industries in Macao from 2012 to 2022.

$$\text{Entropy Index} = \sum_{i=1}^N S_i \ln(1/S_i) \quad (18)$$

Table 1

Calculations, Purposes, and Trends of Financial Innovation Indicators in Macao, 2012–2022

Indicator	Calculation Method	Purpose	Trend
X_1 : Proportion of financial industry employment	Financial industry employees ÷ Total employed personnel × 100%	Reflects sector's activity level and talent pool for traditional financial innovation	Rising annually
X_2 : Financial institutions' value-added ratio	Value added of financial institutions ÷ Financial industry GDP	Measures the economic contribution of financial institutions to traditional financial innovation	Significant increase, especially during pandemic (2020–2022)
X_3 : Loan-to-deposit ratio of financial institutions	Total loans from financial institutions ÷ Total deposits from financial institutions	Indicates liquidity and fund utilization in financial institutions for traditional financial innovation	Steady upward trend
X_4 : Proportion of financial industry financing	Financial industry financing ÷ Total social financing × 100%	Measures capital-raising capacity for traditional financial innovation	Steady upward trend
X_5 : Financial system asset ratio	Total assets of financial institutions ÷ Financial industry GDP	Reflects financial system's size and risk absorption capacity for traditional financial innovation	Significant growth during pandemic
X_6 : Proportion of new financial technology companies	Number of new financial technology companies ÷ Total number of new companies × 100%	Drives financial technology innovation through new company formation	Peaked in 2012, slow growth since
X_7 : Proportion of financial technology investment	Government financial technology funding ÷ Total fiscal expenditure × 100%	Fosters financial technology innovation through government investment	Rebounded during pandemic

Note. Data sourced from Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service (2012–2022) and National Bureau of Statistics of China (2012–2022).

Equation (18) defines the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity. Here, N represents the number of industries in the economy; S_i is the proportion of the added value of the i^{th} industry to the total added value; \ln is the natural logarithm. A larger Entropy Index indicates higher economic diversification, while a smaller Entropy Index indicates higher economic concentration (Research and Economic Analysis Division, 2011; see also Hackbart & Anderson, 1975, for a foundational discussion).

As shown in Figure 3, the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity for Macao shows notable improvement from 2020 to 2022, with index values of 2.20, 2.19, and 2.25, respectively. During this period, Macao's economic diversification reached a relatively high level. However, these changes in industrial structure may represent temporary fluctuations caused by the unique circumstances of the pandemic rather than a fundamental improvement. Achieving industrial diversification in Macao is a long-term and continuous effort. It is essential to adhere to the "1 + 4" economic development strategy while focusing on the development of Macao's competitive industries, such as those reflected in the seven financial innovation indicators (see Table 1).

Figure 2

Trends of Financial Innovation Indicators (X_1 – X_7) in Macao, 2012–2022

Note: Data represent standardized values (z-scores) of seven financial innovation indicators (see Table 1) sourced from Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service (2012–2022) and National Bureau of Statistics of China (2012–2022).

Figure 3

Entropy Index of Economic Diversity in Macao (Production Method), 2002–2022

Note. Adapted from Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service (2022).

5.1.2. Data Sources and Descriptions

This study examines the relationship between the financial innovation system and the industrial diversification system, using data from the Macao region over 11 years from 2012 to 2022. Data were obtained from official government statistics (Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service, 2012–2022, 2022, 2023) and national statistical yearbooks (National Bureau of Statistics of China, 2012–2022). The basic characteristics of the data are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics for Financial Innovation Indicators in Macao, 2012–2022

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
X_1	11	0.0239	0.0349	0.0290	0.0033
X_2	11	0.0368	0.1906	0.0832	0.0508
X_3	11	0.7520	1.0130	0.8895	0.0813
X_4	11	0.1858	0.3329	0.2464	0.0467
X_5	11	2.9176	13.8481	6.0240	3.8754
X_6	11	0.0005	0.0133	0.0021	0.0037
X_7	11	0.0060	0.0163	0.0105	0.0041

Note. Variables X_1 – X_7 correspond to the financial innovation indicators listed in Table 1. Data were sourced from government statistics (Government of Macao Special Administrative Region Statistics and Census Service, 2012–2022) and national statistical yearbooks (National Bureau of Statistics of China, 2012–2022).

Table 3

Correlation Matrix of Financial Innovation Indicators in Macao, 2012–2022

Variable	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5	X_6	X_7
X_1	1.000						
X_2	.835	1.000					
X_3	.940	.866	1.000				
X_4	.831	.940	.852	1.000			
X_5	.812	.981	.828	.924	1.000		
X_6	-.514	-.332	-.555	-.325	-.300	1.000	
X_7	-.172	.041	-.256	-.190	.123	.348	1.000

Note. Variables X_1 – X_7 correspond to the financial innovation indicators listed in Table 1.

5.2. Principal Component Analysis

5.2.1. Test of the Applicability of Data Standardization and Factor Analysis

The original data were standardized, followed by the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett's test of sphericity to assess suitability for factor analysis. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy was 0.725, and Bartlett's test indicated significant correlations among indicators, $\chi^2(21) = 77.231$, $p < 0.001$. These results confirm that the data are suitable for principal component analysis and factor analysis.

5.2.2. Use of Correlation Matrix to Solve the Principal Components

The first two principal components were retained based on their eigenvalues exceeding 1 and a steep slope in the scree plot, while remaining components showed a flatter slope (Table 4). These components account for 86.992% of the total variance, indicating that they capture 86.992% of the information contained in the original seven financial innovation indicators. This suggests that the extracted components provide a reliable basis for evaluating the overall level of financial innovation in Macao. Accordingly, two principal components are retained, namely Principal Component 1 (C_1) and Principal Component 2 (C_2).

Table 4

Variance Explained by Principal Components of Financial Innovation in Macao, 2012–2022

Component	Initial Eigenvalue			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Variance %	Accumulated %	Total	Variance %	Accumulated %
1	4.765	68.066	68.066	4.765	68.066	68.066
2	1.325	18.926	86.992	1.325	18.926	86.992
3	0.615	8.785	95.778			
4	0.203	2.905	98.682			
5	0.060	0.854	99.536			
6	0.017	0.250	99.786			
7	0.015	0.214	100.000			

Note. Components with eigenvalues greater than 1 were extracted by principal component analysis.

5.2.3. Calculation of Principal Component Coefficients

The expressions of each principal component are calculated according to the formula:

$$C_1 = 0.4302X_1 + 0.4361X_2 + 0.4398X_3 + 0.4325X_4 + 0.4260X_5 - 0.2400X_6 - 0.0747X_7 \quad (19)$$

$$C_2 = -0.0530X_1 + 0.2233X_2 - 0.1103X_3 + 0.0756X_4 + 0.2867X_5 + 0.5169X_6 + 0.7610X_7 \quad (20)$$

In Principal Component 1 (C_1), the magnitude of the coefficients of the proportion of financial industry employment (X_1), the financial institutions' value-added ratio (X_2), the loan-to-deposit ratio of financial institutions (X_3), the proportion of financial industry financing (X_4), and the financial system asset ratio (X_5) are larger than those of other indicators (see Table 1). Therefore, C_1 comprehensively reflects these five financial innovation indicators and represents the innovation level and capability of Macao's "traditional financial innovation."

In Principal Component 2 (C_2), the coefficients of the proportion of new financial technology companies (X_6) and the proportion of financial technology investment (X_7) are more prominent. Thus, C_2 is primarily characterized by these two indicators and represents the level and capability of Macao's "financial technology innovation."

5.2.4. Calculation of the Principal Component Score

Table 5 shows the principal component composite score (C). Its expression is as follows:

$$C = 0.6807C_1 + 0.1893C_2 \quad (21)$$

Table 5
Principal Component Scores and Rankings for Financial Innovation in Macao, 2012–2022

Year	Principal Component 1 (C_1) Score	Principal Component 2 (C_2) Score	Principal Component Composite Score (C)	Rank
2012	-3.3732	2.3021	-1.8604	11
2013	-2.2685	0.5439	-1.4412	10
2014	-1.3974	0.0840	-0.9353	9
2015	-0.7627	-1.0545	-0.7188	7
2016	-0.8807	-0.9970	-0.7882	8
2017	-0.1640	-1.0240	-0.3055	5
2018	-0.1795	-1.1388	-0.3378	6
2019	0.1879	-1.0928	-0.0790	4
2020	1.9371	0.7097	1.4529	3
2021	3.1575	0.6173	2.2662	2
2022	3.7434	1.0502	2.7470	1

Note. Principal component composite scores (C) reflect weighted combination of C_1 and C_2 per Equation (21). Indicators X_1 – X_5 contribute to C_1 , and X_6 – X_7 to C_2 , per Table 1.

From the Principal Component 1 (C_1) score, the years with higher values are 2020, 2021, and 2022, indicating a relatively higher level of traditional financial innovation (e.g., banking, insurance) during this period. A key contributing factor may be the COVID-19 pandemic. With restrictions on offline activities, the traditional financial industry faced unprecedented challenges, spurring faster innovation to meet evolving market demands and adapt to changing conditions. Over the 2012–2022 period, the traditional financial innovation level shows a consistent upward trend, with C_1 scores rising from -3.3732 in 2012 to 3.7434 in 2022.

From the Principal Component 2 (C_2) score, the years with higher values are 2012, 2020, 2021, and 2022, indicating relatively higher levels of financial technology innovation. In 2012, influenced by a global surge in financial technology investment (e.g., mobile payments, blockchain), Macao experienced a significant peak in financial technology development, with a C_2 score of 2.3021. However, a subsequent decline occurred, with sustained stagnation from 2013 to 2019, likely due to stricter financial supervision policies implemented nationwide from 2013. In response, the Macao government aligned with national regulatory frameworks, imposing tighter controls on financial technology development. From 2020 to 2022, the COVID-19 pandemic stimulated renewed innovation in financial technology, with C_2 scores recovering to positive values (0.7097, 0.6173, and 1.0502, respectively).

From the principal component composite score (C), calculated as $C = 0.6807C_1 + 0.1893C_2$ per Equation (21), the years 2020–2022 show the highest values (1.4529, 2.2662, 2.7470, respectively), reflecting comprehensive improvements in financial innovation during the pandemic. Over the entire timeline, Macao's financial innovation level also shows a consistent upward trend. The coefficient of C_1 (0.6807) exceeds C_2 (0.1893), as C_1 includes five indicators (X_1 – X_5) compared to C_2 's two indicators (X_6 – X_7), per Table 1. Another possible reason is that traditional financial innovation (C_1) is relatively easier to achieve, driven by strong market demand during the pandemic, while financial technology innovation (C_2) requires higher resource and time costs.

5.3. Factor Analysis

5.3.1. Derivation of Initial Factor Loadings Using the Principal Component Method

Factor analysis is conducted on seven financial innovation indicators (see Table 1) in Macao over the past eleven years, using the principal component method to determine the initial factor loadings. The results yield two common factors, namely Common Factor 1 (F_1) and Common Factor 2 (F_2), with a cumulative contribution rate of 86.992%. This indicates that the two extracted common factors explain 86.992% of the variance in the original seven indicators, effectively preserving the original information and demonstrating strong representativeness.

5.3.2. Factor Analysis Model for the Financial Innovation Indicator System in Macao

A variance maximization orthogonal rotation is applied to the initial factor loading matrix to enhance the interpretability of the factor structure. Based on the rotated loadings, the following factor analysis model is established for Macao's financial innovation indicator system:

$$X_1 = 0.888F_1 - 0.310F_2 \quad (22)$$

$$X_2 = 0.986F_1 - 0.006F_2 \quad (23)$$

$$X_3 = 0.891F_1 - 0.379F_2 \quad (24)$$

$$X_4 = 0.933F_1 - 0.168F_2 \quad (25)$$

$$X_5 = 0.984F_1 + 0.070F_2 \quad (26)$$

$$X_6 = -0.346F_1 + 0.714F_2 \quad (27)$$

$$X_7 = 0.077F_1 + 0.888F_2 \quad (28)$$

According to the factor analysis model, Common Factor 1 (F_1) is primarily determined by five financial innovation indicators (see Table 1): the proportion of financial industry employment (X_1), the financial institutions' value-added ratio (X_2), the loan-to-deposit ratio of financial institutions (X_3), the proportion of financial industry financing (X_4), and the financial system asset ratio (X_5). The loadings of these five indicators on F_1 all exceed 85%, indicating that this factor is closely associated with traditional financial business activities. Therefore, F_1 is designated as Traditional Financial Innovation. Common Factor 2 (F_2) is mainly composed of two indicators: the proportion of new financial technology companies (X_6) and the proportion of financial technology investment (X_7). Both indicators have loadings exceeding 70% on F_2 , reflecting a strong emphasis on technological aspects. Hence, F_2 is referred to as Financial Technology Innovation.

5.3.3. Factor Equation

According to the factor score coefficient, the factor equation is obtained as follows:

$$F_1 = 0.177X_1 + 0.244X_2 + 0.169X_3 + 0.209X_4 + 0.255X_5 + 0.014X_6 + 0.144X_7 \quad (29)$$

$$F_2 = -0.097X_1 + 0.134X_2 - 0.146X_3 + 0.011X_4 + 0.188X_5 + 0.462X_6 + 0.646X_7 \quad (30)$$

5.3.4. Factor Score and Factor Composite Score

The factor scores calculated based on the factor equation are shown in Table 6. In addition, the factor composite score, denoted as Q , represents the overall evaluation index of

financial innovation. It is calculated as the weighted sum of the extracted common factors F_1 and F_2 , with weights 0.6455 and 0.2244, respectively, thereby summarizing the joint influence of the original variables. The equation for Q is as follows:

$$Q = 0.6455F_1 + 0.2244F_2 \quad (31)$$

Table 6

Factor Scores and Rankings for Financial Innovation in Macao, 2012–2022

Year	F_1	F_2	Q	Rank
2012	-0.9543	2.3406	-0.0907	4
2013	-0.8750	0.7326	-0.4004	9
2014	-0.5974	0.2408	-0.3316	6
2015	-0.5816	-0.7898	-0.5527	10
2016	-0.6203	-0.7272	-0.5636	11
2017	-0.3103	-0.8377	-0.3883	7
2018	-0.3438	-0.9318	-0.4310	8
2019	-0.1710	-0.9385	-0.3210	5
2020	1.0200	0.3577	0.7387	3
2021	1.5372	0.1309	1.0216	2
2022	1.8965	0.4224	1.3190	1

Note. Factor composite scores (Q) reflect weighted combination of F_1 and F_2 per Equation (31).

While the results of factor analysis are generally consistent with those of principal component analysis, some differences do exist. Principal component analysis emphasizes variance, whereas factor analysis focuses on covariance through rotation. The scores and trends of Common Factor 1 (F_1) and Common Factor 2 (F_2) resemble those of Principal Component 1 (C_1) and Principal Component 2 (C_2), but factor scores have a narrower range due to rotation (e.g., F_1 : -0.9543 to 1.8965, Table 6 vs. C_1 : -3.3732 to 3.7434, Table 5). Rotation in factor analysis emphasizes covariance, leading to slightly higher Q scores in non-pandemic years with strong financial technology activity (e.g., 2012: Q = -0.0907, Rank 4; 2019: Q = -0.3210, Rank 5, Table 6) compared to other non-pandemic years (e.g., 2016: Q = -0.5636, Rank 11, Table 6). According to factor analysis, the highest levels of financial innovation occur in the pandemic years (2020–2022: Q = 0.7387 to 1.3190, Ranks 1–3, Table 6), with 2012 and 2019 showing relatively higher Q scores among non-pandemic years. In contrast, principal component analysis identifies the top six years as 2017–2022 (C = -0.3378 to 2.7470, Ranks 1–6, Table 5). The trend chart comparing these results is shown in Figure 4.

The timeline can be divided into three distinct stages as follows:

Stage One (2012–2014): Financial Technology Innovation Greater than Traditional Financial Innovation. This period marks the emergence of the financial technology innovation wave. During this stage, the scores for financial technology innovation (C_2 and F_2) are positive (e.g., F_2 = 2.3406 in 2012, 0.2408 in 2014, Table 6), indicating early momentum in financial technology development. However, overall financial innovation (Q) remains negative (e.g., Q = -0.0907 in 2012, -0.3316 in 2014), as traditional financial innovation (C_1 and F_1) scores are low (e.g., F_1 = -0.9543 in 2012, Table 6). As a new phenomenon, financial technology innovation carries inherent risks. The introduction of China's first wave of strong financial regulation in 2013 contributed to the subsequent decline of financial technology innovation following its 2012 peak.

Figure 4

Trends in Principal Component Scores and Factor Scores for Financial Innovation in Macao, 2012–2022

Stage Two (2015–2019): Balanced Development. In the early years of this stage (2015–2016), events such as stock market crashes, economic slowdown, and persistent weakness in commodity prices posed challenges to overall financial development. Although the scores for both traditional financial innovation and financial technology innovation remain below zero during this period, they gradually rise in parallel, indicating balanced and moderate progress. In the later years (2017–2019), traditional financial innovation (C_1 and F_1) begins to outperform financial technology innovation (C_2 and F_2), showing a more pronounced upward trend, while financial technology innovation begins to decline slightly.

Stage Three (2020–2022): Traditional Financial Innovation Greater than Financial Technology Innovation. This stage corresponds to the COVID-19 pandemic. Financial innovation overall shows a rapid upward trend, with all principal component scores and factor scores exceeding zero. Traditional financial innovation demonstrates stronger growth compared to financial technology innovation. Despite some recovery, financial technology innovation has not returned to its 2012 peak levels.

This stage-based analysis highlights the dynamic relationship between traditional financial innovation and financial technology innovation in Macao, influenced by regulatory, economic, and external public health factors.

5.4. Moderating Effects

According to the principle of moderating effects, this study examines moderation by treating the principal component scores C_1 , C_2 , and C , as well as the factor scores F_1 , F_2 , and Q , as independent variables (X), with the industrial diversification indicator as the dependent variable (Y), and the pandemic indicator as the moderator variable (Z). During the pandemic period (2020, 2021, and 2022), the value of Z is set to 1; for all other years, representing the non-pandemic period, Z is set to 0. Interaction terms, namely, $C_1 \times Z$, $C_2 \times Z$, $C \times Z$, $F_1 \times Z$, $F_2 \times Z$, and $Q \times Z$, are constructed to test for moderation. A significant interaction term confirms a moderating effect. The results of these analyses are presented in Tables 7, 8, and 9.

Table 7

Moderating Effects of Pandemic (Z) on the Impact of Traditional Financial Innovation (C₁), Financial Technology Innovation (C₂), and Overall Financial Innovation (C) on Industrial Diversification (Y) in Macao, 2012–2022

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Constant	1.850*** (67.337)	1.823*** (40.985)	1.837*** (40.854)	Constant	1.850*** (21.538)	1.680*** (58.089)	1.679*** (58.366)
C ₁	0.117*** (8.887)	0.099*** (3.661)	0.112*** (3.926)	C ₂	-0.001 (-0.014)	-0.113*** (-4.649)	-0.115*** (-4.755)
Z		0.098 (0.778)	0.310 (1.433)	Z		0.623*** (10.410)	0.422* (2.101)
C ₁ × Z			-0.090 (-1.190)	C ₂ × Z			0.256 (1.043)
R ²	0.898	0.905	0.921	R ²	0.000	0.931	0.941
Adjusted R ²	0.886	0.881	0.887	Adjusted R ²	-0.111	0.914	0.915
F	F(1, 9) = 78.971****	F(2, 8) = 38.055****	F(3, 7) = 27.166****	F	F(1, 9) = 0.000 p = 0.989	F(2, 8) = 54.184****	F(3, 7) = 36.885****
Δ R ²	0.898	0.007	0.016	Δ R ²	0.000	0.931	0.009
Δ F	F(1, 9) = 78.971****	F(1, 8) = 0.605 p = 0.459	F(1, 7) = 1.417 p = 0.273	Δ F	F(1, 9) = 0.000 p = 0.989	F(1, 8) = 108.365****	F(1, 7) = 1.089 p = 0.331

Note. Coefficients are standardized regression coefficients (β), representing the change in the dependent variable (Y) in standard deviations per standard deviation increase in the predictor, holding other variables constant.

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.001$. The value of t is enclosed in parentheses. Z = pandemic indicator, coded 0 for non-pandemic years (2012–2019) and 1 for pandemic years (2020–2022).

In each Model 1, the coefficient of traditional financial innovation is statistically significant for C_1 , F_1 , C , and Q . Specifically, for C_1 , a one-unit increase in traditional financial innovation corresponds to a 0.117-unit increase in industrial diversification; for F_1 , a one-unit increase results in a 0.246-unit increase. For the composite scores, a one-unit increase in overall financial innovation leads to a 0.169-unit increase in industrial diversification based on C , and a 0.307-unit increase based on Q . Traditional finance is closely linked to daily economic activities, including personal savings and loan services for residents, as well as financing needs for small and medium-sized enterprises, particularly in times of economic stress such as during the pandemic. The unexpected outbreak of COVID-19 disrupted the normal operations of traditional financial services in terms of both time and space, prompting accelerated innovation within the sector. These results highlight the important role of traditional financial innovation in promoting industrial diversification.

In each Model 1, the coefficients of financial technology innovation—represented by C_2 and F_2 —are not statistically significant. Although technology and artificial intelligence are advancing rapidly on a global scale, their impact at the regional level often depends on a combination of local economic, political, and cultural factors. In the context of Macao, the development of financial technology innovation faces several constraints. On one hand, it is subject to considerable regulatory oversight, which has limited its growth and resulted in relatively passive and slower development. On the other hand, during the pandemic, the proportion of financial resources allocated to technological investment increased substantially. This reallocation may have reduced the funding available to other sectors. The expansion of financial technology innovation typically requires substantial investments in capital, time, labor, and resources and often involves long trial-and-error cycles. As a result, it may temporarily hinder the development of other industries and pose challenges to industrial diversification. Nonetheless, it is expected that in the coming years, the long-term advantages of financial technology innovation will become increasingly evident.

Table 8

Moderating Effects of Pandemic (Z) on the Impact of Traditional Financial Innovation (F₁), Financial Technology Innovation (F₂) on Industrial Diversification (Y) in Macao, 2012–2022

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Constant	1.850*** (52.486)	1.861*** (22.006)	1.949*** (19.997)	Constant	1.850*** (22.287)	1.700*** (61.505)	1.700*** (59.910)
F ₁	0.246*** (6.667)	0.264* (2.029)	0.422** (2.650)	F ₂	-0.069 (-0.798)	-0.120*** (-4.768)	-0.121*** (-4.687)
Z		-0.039 (-0.138)	0.188 (0.632)	Z		0.549*** (10.237)	0.464*** (3.728)
F ₁ × Z			-0.370 (-1.520)	F ₂ × Z			0.284 (0.770)
R ²	0.832	0.832	0.874	R ²	0.066	0.934	0.939
Adjusted R ²	0.813	0.790	0.820	Adjusted R ²	-0.038	0.917	0.913
F	F(1, 9) = 44.446****	F(2, 8) = 19.811****	F(3, 7) = 16.140***	F	F(1, 9) = 0.637 p = 0.445	F(2, 8) = 56.389****	F(3, 7) = 35.874****
Δ R ²	0.832	0.000	0.042	Δ R ²	0.066	0.868	0.005
Δ F	F(1, 9) = 44.446****	F(1, 8) = 0.019 p = 0.893	F(1, 7) = 2.310 p = 0.172	Δ F	F(1, 9) = 0.637 p = 0.445	F(1, 8) = 104.794****	F(1, 7) = 0.592 p = 0.467

Note. Coefficients are standardized regression coefficients (β), representing the change in the dependent variable (Y) in standard deviations per standard deviation increase in the predictor, holding other variables constant.

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.001$. The value of t is enclosed in parentheses. Z = pandemic indicator, coded 0 for non-pandemic years (2012–2019) and 1 for pandemic years (2020–2022).

Table 9

Moderating Effects of Pandemic (Z) on the Impact of Overall Financial Innovation (C, Q) on Industrial Diversification (Y) in Macao, 2012–2022

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Constant	1.850*** (61.590)	1.850*** (31.073)	1.887*** (30.881)	Constant	1.850*** (34.209)	1.591*** (15.090)	1.422*** (11.767)
C	0.169*** (8.037)	0.169** (2.940)	0.214** (3.455)	Q	0.307*** (3.702)	-0.319 (-1.314)	-0.757** (-2.566)
Z		-0.000 (-0.001)	0.255 (1.040)	Z		0.950** (2.674)	0.702* (2.174)
C × Z			-0.181 (-1.466)	Q × Z			0.845* (2.062)
R ²	0.878	0.878	0.906	R ²	0.604	0.791	0.870
Adjusted R ²	0.864	0.847	0.866	Adjusted R ²	0.560	0.738	0.814
F	F(1, 9) = 64.595****	F(2, 8) = 28.709****	F(3, 7) = 22.602****	F	F(1, 9) = 13.705***	F(2, 8) = 15.112***	F(3, 7) = 15.586***
Δ R ²	0.878	0.000	0.029	Δ R ²	0.604	0.187	0.079
Δ F	F(1, 9) = 64.595****	F(1, 8) = 0.000 p = 0.999	F(1, 7) = 2.148 p = 0.186	Δ F	F(1, 9) = 13.705***	F(1, 8) = 7.152**	F(1, 7) = 4.251*

Note. Coefficients are standardized regression coefficients (β), representing the change in the dependent variable (Y) in standard deviations per standard deviation increase in the predictor, holding other variables constant.

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.001$. The value of t is enclosed in parentheses. Z = pandemic indicator, coded 0 for non-pandemic years (2012–2019) and 1 for pandemic years (2020–2022).

In summary, both analytical approaches indicate that traditional financial innovation and financial technology innovation exert a significant positive impact on industrial

diversification. Moreover, the influence observed through factor analysis is greater than that derived from principal component analysis.

In each Model 3, the interaction terms for C_1 , C_2 , C , F_1 , and F_2 are not statistically significant, with minimal changes in adjusted R^2 and non-significant changes in the F -statistic (ΔF) from Model 2 to Model 3, suggesting no moderating effect in these cases (Tables 7–9). In contrast, when using Q as the independent variable, the interaction coefficient $Q \times Z$ is statistically significant ($p < .1$), and the change in the F -statistic (ΔF) from Model 2 to Model 3 is significant, confirming a moderating effect. The coefficient of overall financial innovation (Q) in Model 1 is significantly positive ($\beta = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$, Table 9), and the interaction term ($Q \times Z$) in Model 3 is significantly positive ($\beta = 0.845$, $p < 0.1$, Table 9). The significant interaction term indicates that the pandemic mitigates the negative relationship between overall financial innovation (Q) and industrial diversification (Y) in non-pandemic years, enhancing diversification during the pandemic (Table 9).

$$Y = 1.422 - 0.757Q + 0.702Z + 0.845(Q \times Z) \quad (32)$$

Significance levels of the coefficients in Equation (32) are indicated in Table 9, where the constant is significant at $p < 0.01$, coefficient of Q at $p < 0.05$, coefficient of Z at $p < 0.1$, and coefficient of $Q \times Z$ at $p < 0.1$.

In addition, this study independently verifies the impact of financial innovation on industrial diversification by conducting separate regression analyses using C_1 and C_2 , as well as F_1 and F_2 , with industrial diversification (Y) as the dependent variable. The results are presented in Tables 10 and 11. C_1 , F_1 , and F_2 show a significant positive impact on Y , while C_2 does not. This may be attributed to the long-term costs and risks associated with trial-and-error processes in technological finance. Moreover, such investments may divert resources from other sectors, potentially hindering overall industrial diversification. Although F_2 's individual effect is significant ($p = 0.053$, Table 11), its contribution to industrial diversification appears enhanced when considered alongside F_1 , as suggested by the significant overall effect of Q (Table 9). This suggests that financial technology innovation must operate in conjunction with traditional financial innovation to contribute effectively to industrial diversification.

The impact of overall financial innovation (Q) on industrial diversification (Y) varies by pandemic conditions (Z), as shown in Equation (32) and Table 9. In non-pandemic years ($Z = 0$, 2012–2019), overall financial innovation has a significant negative effect on industrial diversification ($\beta = -0.757$, $p < 0.05$). In contrast, during pandemic years ($Z = 1$, 2020–2022), financial innovation enhanced diversification ($\beta = 0.088$, which is obtained from -0.757 of $Q + 0.845$ of the interaction term $Q \times Z$). The negative effect in non-pandemic periods is largely attributable to strict regulatory constraints (e.g., gaming concession limits and anti-money laundering rules) and a policy focus on Macao's gaming industry, which concentrated resources and limited financial innovation's effectiveness. During the pandemic, the gaming industry's stagnation spurred increased adoption of online financial services, contactless digital payments, and financial technology, fostering a resilient, inclusive economic and social ecosystem in Macao that enhanced diversification by supporting small and medium-sized enterprises.

Table 10

Effects of Traditional Financial Innovation (C_1) and Financial Technology Innovation (C_2) on Industrial Diversification (Y) in Macao, 2012–2022

	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	VIF	Tolerance
Constant	1.850	0.029	63.491	< 0.001	-	-
C_1	0.117	0.014	8.379	< 0.001	1.000	1.000
C_2	-0.001	0.027	-0.036	0.972	1.000	1.000
R^2	0.898					
Adjusted R^2	0.872					
DW	1.979					
<i>F</i>	$F(2, 8) = 35.104, p < 0.001$					

Note. A Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic value of approximately 2 (e.g., 1.979) suggests no significant autocorrelation, based on standard thresholds for small samples.

Table 11

Effects of Traditional Financial Innovation (F_1) and Financial Technology Innovation (F_2) on Industrial Diversification (Y) in Macao, 2012–2022

	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	VIF	Tolerance
Constant	1.850	0.029	63.489	< 0.001	-	-
F_1	0.246	0.031	8.064	< 0.001	1.000	1.000
F_2	-0.069	0.031	-2.274	= 0.053	1.000	1.000
R^2	0.898					
Adjusted R^2	0.872					
DW	1.979					
<i>F</i>	$F(2, 8) = 35.101, p < 0.001$					

Note. A Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic value of approximately 2 (e.g., 1.979) suggests no significant autocorrelation, based on standard thresholds for small samples.

6. Discussion

6.1. Financial Innovation and Industrial Diversification: Contributions and Findings (2012–2022)

This study investigates how financial innovation drives industrial diversification in Macao, a gaming-centric economy, from 2012 to 2022. Financial innovation—encompassing traditional services like banking and loans and modern financial technology like mobile payments and blockchain—was analyzed using principal component analysis and factor analysis. Principal component analysis grouped seven financial indicators (X_1 – X_7) into traditional financial innovation (C_1) and financial technology innovation (C_2), both being weighted to form the overall financial innovation: $C = 0.6807C_1 + 0.1893C_2$, per Equation (21). Factor analysis produced similar dimensions: traditional financial innovation (F_1), financial technology innovation (F_2), both being weighted to form the overall financial innovation: $Q = 0.6455F_1 + 0.2244F_2$, per Equation (31). This section outlines the study's theoretical and

methodological contributions, including the use of composite scores to address analytical challenges, followed by empirical findings on how financial innovation drives diversification, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic.

6.1.1. Theoretical and Methodological Contribution: Use of Composite Scores

A key contribution of this study lies in its use of principal component scores and factor scores (C_1, C_2, F_1, F_2) as predictors in regression analyses, rather than the seven raw financial innovation indicators (X_1-X_7). This approach addresses several theoretical and methodological challenges. First, the seven indicators (X_1-X_7) are highly correlated (e.g., correlation of 0.940 between X_2 and X_4 , Table 3), posing a risk of multicollinearity, which can inflate variance and produce unreliable regression coefficients. Principal component analysis and factor analysis reduce these indicators into two theoretically meaningful constructs: traditional financial innovation (C_1, F_1 , capturing X_1-X_5) and financial technology innovation (C_2, F_2 , capturing X_6-X_7), which account for 86.992% of the variance (Table 4) while eliminating multicollinearity (VIF = 1.000, Tables 10–11). This dimensionality reduction aligns with the study's framework (Figure 1), which distinguishes traditional financial innovation and financial technology innovation as distinct drivers of industrial diversification (Sections 5.2.3 and 5.3.2). Using principal component scores and factor scores simplifies interpretation by focusing on these latent constructs rather than the seven individual indicators, enhancing clarity for policymakers and marketing scholars. Additionally, with only 11 annual observations (2012–2022), using seven predictors would risk overfitting and reduce statistical power (Section 6.4). The principal component scores and factor scores preserve statistical efficiency, making this approach a robust methodological contribution to studying financial innovation in small economies like Macao. Having established this methodological foundation, the next subsection explores how these composite scores reveal financial innovation's impact on Macao's industrial diversification.

6.1.2. Empirical Findings on Financial Innovation's Impact

Both principal component analysis and factor analysis show financial innovation peaked during the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022), with traditional financial innovation (C_1, F_1) outpacing financial technology innovation (C_2, F_2), which peaked in 2012 due to global mobile payment and blockchain trends. In 2022, overall financial innovation reached its highest levels ($C = 2.7470$, Table 5, $Q = 1.3190$, Table 6). Regression analyses (Tables 7 to 11) reveal that traditional financial innovation strongly enhances industrial diversification, measured by the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity (C_1 's $\beta = 0.117$, $p < 0.001$, Table 10; F_1 's $\beta = 0.246$, $p < 0.001$, Table 11), while overall financial innovation has a positive baseline effect (C 's $\beta = 0.169$, $p < 0.01$; Q 's $\beta = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$, Table 9, Model 1) but is moderated by the pandemic. Financial technology innovation's direct effect is weaker (C_2 's $\beta = -0.001$, $p = 0.972$, Table 10; F_2 's $\beta = -0.069$, $p = 0.053$, Table 11), but its marginal contribution via Q suggests value when integrated with traditional financial innovation.

The pandemic, coded as Z (0 = non-pandemic years 2012–2019, 1 = pandemic years 2020–2022), moderated this relationship. Table 9 shows that overall financial innovation (Q) reduced industrial diversification in non-pandemic years ($\beta = -0.757$, $p < 0.05$) but enhanced diversification during the pandemic ($\beta = 0.088$, which is obtained from -0.757 of $Q + 0.845$ of the interaction term $Q \times Z$). This shift reflects financial technology's role, such as AI-driven customer targeting and digital payments, in enhancing diversification during the pandemic.

These findings inform the subsequent section, which proposes policy and managerial strategies to harness financial innovation for sustainable economic diversification in Macao.

6.2. Policy and Managerial Implications and Recommendations

The findings highlight financial innovation's role in driving industrial diversification in Macao, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022). The following subsections outline policy and managerial strategies to leverage these insights, which foster sustainable economic growth in Macao's gaming-centric economy.

6.2.1. Recommendations for Policy-Driven Economic Diversification

Macao's economy, heavily reliant on gaming, faced a severe downturn during the pandemic, exposing its mono-industrial vulnerabilities. Financial innovation, particularly through mobile payment applications, showed resilience, outpacing gaming's economic contribution by 2022 ($C = 2.7470$, Table 5; $Q = 1.3190$, Table 6). To sustain this momentum, policymakers should establish regulatory sandboxes to test blockchain-based financial applications, ensuring innovation aligns with risk management. These sandboxes can foster financial inclusion and cross-border integration within the Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macao Greater Bay Area. Additionally, targeted incentives for mobile payment platforms, such as MPay, can enhance consumer trust and adoption, addressing cultural barriers, such as consumer animosity toward foreign financial technologies in collectivist markets (see also Ang et al., 2004; Jung et al., 2002; Leong et al., 2008). It can be inferred from Pornpitakpan's (2004) review of source credibility that promoting local platforms with high perceived credibility can mitigate resistance, as credible sources enhance persuasion across cultures. Culturally aligned financial technology interfaces may also enhance adoption by increasing perceived trustworthiness.

To further support diversification, the government should increase fiscal support for financial innovation, as evidenced by its significant impact during the pandemic ($C = 2.7470$, Table 5; $Q = 1.3190$, Table 6), while developing rational budget allocations to optimize resource distribution. Capital should be directed toward industries with high innovation potential, such as technology and cultural industries, which align with Macao's "1 + 4" economic development strategy (i.e., integrated tourism and leisure plus "Big Health" industry; modern financial services; high and new technology; convention, exhibition, sports, and commercial and trade industries). Moreover, policymakers should adjust financial policies in response to evolving economic conditions, as the study's moderating effects show that financial innovation enhanced diversification during the pandemic (Table 9). A balanced approach to financial technology innovation, fostering flexibility while maintaining regulatory oversight, will promote resilient growth, supported by Qamruzzaman and Wei's (2018) findings that financial innovation stimulates long-term economic growth in emerging markets. These measures will strengthen the integration of traditional and financial technology innovation, supporting Macao's sustainable economic development.

6.2.2. Recommendations for Managerial and Marketing Strategies

To capitalize on financial innovation's high levels during 2020–2022 ($C = 1.4529$ – 2.7470 , Table 5; $Q = 0.7387$ – 1.3190 , Table 6), managers in Macao's financial and hospitality sectors should integrate traditional and financial technology innovations. Traditional financial institutions should collaborate with financial technology companies to enhance competitiveness, aligning with the study's findings that traditional financial innovation (C_1, F_1) strongly drives diversification (Tables 10–11). Sachet marketing strategies (Pornpitakpan et al., 2025; Sy-Changco et al., 2011), offering affordable financial services to low-income or variety-seeking consumers, can further enhance adoption. Drawing on results from Pornpitakpan et al. (2017) and Pornpitakpan and Han (2013), high-quality retail service for financial technology applications may spur impulse adoption, particularly in hospitality settings like

tourism and retail, where personalized mobile payment offers enhance customer experiences. For example, integrating mobile payment applications with tourism services (e.g., digital ticketing for cultural attractions) can attract Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macao Greater Bay Area visitors, supporting Macao's hospitality-driven diversification. These strategies align with Macao's tourism-centric economy and promote sustainable growth by enhancing consumer trust and engagement in financial technologies.

Managers should also address psychological barriers, such as unrealistic optimism (Pornpitakpan & Green, 2007, 2010) about traditional financial services (C_1), which may reduce financial technology innovation uptake (C_2) during crises. Digital marketing on platforms like Weibo can amplify financial technology innovation awareness, leveraging negativity biases to drive engagement, as research (Pornpitakpan & Wang, 2025) suggests that negative publicity usually drives engagement more than positive publicity does.

6.3. Limitations of the Study

Building on the study's findings, it is necessary to address several limitations that influence the interpretation of the results. First, the dataset, limited to 11 annual observations from 2012 to 2022, restricts statistical power, particularly when examining moderating effects. As indicated in Table 9, while the $Q \times Z$ interaction was significant ($p < 0.1$), other interactions (e.g., $C \times Z$) did not reach significance, potentially due to the small sample size. Additionally, the financial technology indicator "proportion of new financial technology companies" (X_6) shows a peak in 2012 followed by a decline (Figure 2), which may reflect data reporting inconsistencies or regulatory changes in Macao's financial sector. Triangulating with firm-level data or qualitative evidence could enhance the validity of these observations. Moreover, the lack of a standardized framework for measuring financial innovation in Macao poses a challenge, complicating the selection and comparability of indicators across the study period. Finally, this study uses regression analysis, which does not necessarily imply causation between variables.

6.4. Future Research Directions

The findings of this study highlight several avenues for advancing research on financial innovation and industrial diversification in Macao. First, to address the limitation of low statistical power due to 11 annual observations (2012–2022), future studies should utilize higher-frequency data (e.g., quarterly or monthly) or longer time horizons to enhance reliability and detect moderating effects more robustly (Section 6.3). Furthermore, exploring additional moderators beyond the pandemic, such as policy changes or non-pandemic economic shocks, could clarify the dynamic role of financial innovation in diversification, building on the moderating effect model.

Researchers should consider alternative economic indicators beyond the Entropy Index of Economic Diversity to assess financial innovation's impact, particularly in marketing, international business, and hospitality contexts. For example, examining sector-specific growth metrics could isolate financial technology's contributions to Macao's tourism and retail sectors. Moreover, cross-regional comparisons with financial hubs like Singapore and Hong Kong could reveal cultural influences on financial technology adoption, including barriers posed by consumer animosity, as noted in collectivist settings (see Ang et al., 2004; Jung et al., 2002; Leong et al., 2008).

Additionally, investigating impulse buying behaviors in financial technology contexts, particularly in Macao's collectivist culture, could optimize application interfaces and retail service quality, enhancing consumer engagement in tourism and retail. Similarly, research on regulatory sandboxes for blockchain applications and incentives for mobile payment platforms could inform policies for financial inclusion and cross-border integration within the

Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macao Greater Bay Area. The growing overlap between digital communication and finance, as evidenced by the findings of Pornpitakpan and Wang (2025) that social media discussions influenced stock prices, also warrants further exploration. Studies should examine how platforms like Weibo shape financial technology adoption and economic outcomes in Macao.

Finally, several key questions await future investigation: Does industrial diversification drive financial innovation, or vice versa? How does financial technology adoption shape Macao's sustainable role in the Greater Bay Area? Long-term studies on financial technology's social and economic impacts, particularly in hospitality and cross-border markets, are essential to ensure resilient growth.

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